

Concept Note on Composite Fluoride Vulnerability/Risk Zone

Fluoride in groundwater is mostly of geological origin. Intake of fluoride in excess amounts, mostly via drinking water (other sources are food, industrial gas and excessive use of toothpaste), causes 'fluorosis' effecting the teeth and bones (WHO, 2006). The natural sources of fluoride are fluorite, fluorapatite, and cryolite, whereas anthropogenic sources include coal burning, oil refining, steel production, brick-making industries, and phosphatic fertilizer plants (Jha et al.,2011). The prominent health hazard due to fluoride includes fluorosis which remains a significant problem in many states of India like Andhra Pradesh, Tamilnadu, Gujarat, Rajasthan, Punjab, Haryana, Bihar, Kerala including Karnataka (Susheela AK, 1999). The principal sources of fluoride available to human being are drinking water and foods such as fish, milk, tea and crops. Moreover, the uptake of fluoride from contaminated irrigation water to the cultivated crops may ultimately enter the human food chain through intake of rice, wheat, pulses, vegetables and fruits.

Many research studies have been conducted to estimate fluoride health risk caused due to exposure to contaminated water, food and air. These studies are subjected to considering fluoride concentration of exposure pathways (water, food and air) and dental symptoms associated with it. Present way of assessing fluorosis is by using Dean's Index and Community Fluorosis Index, CFI (Symptoms based approach to assess prevalence of fluorosis). Here, the aim is to develop a framework to determine the prevalence of fluorosis and a decision-making tool for policy makers.

Here, we have introduced variables which act as an indicator for fluorosis severity:

- Fluoride Concentration in water(or exposure through other pathways)
- Income of household
- Nutrition
- Location(Geology)
- Education/Awareness/Capacity Development
- Interventions

Each indicator variable mentioned will be used and according to one's judgment will be given certain weights to make all variables come under one vertical to establish vulnerability assessment of a given area. The weights will be assigned in the range of 0-5, where 0 indicates no risk while 5 represents high risk. The weighted variables will be mapped in GIS platform to know the distribution of the indicator variable in the region.

1. Fluoride Concentration in water(or exposure through other pathways):

The measured concentration of fluoride in water and its corresponding symptoms on human when exposed can be used to assign weights.

Fluoride Concentration(mg/l or ppm)	Effect on Human Health	Probable Weights
<0.5	Conducive for dental carries	-
0.5-1.5	Promotes development of strong bones	0
1.5-2.5	Promotes dental fluorosis in children	3
2.5-4.0	Promotes dental fluorosis in children	4
4.0-5.0	Promotes dental and skeletal fluorosis	4
>5.0	Promotes crippling skeletal fluorosis and possibly cancer	5

2. Income of household

The income indicator variable is divided into three categories: Lower, Middle and High Income class. This variable will help to understand which section of people are vulnerable and are prone or susceptible to be affected by fluorosis.

As per one's individual judgment the weights have been assigned to each category:

- Lower Income: 4-5
- Middle Income: 2-3
- Higher Income: 0-1

3. Nutrition

Nutrition is one of the factors through human attains immunity. A well balanced diet would help one to overcome certain diseases and fluorosis is one of them. It is seen in various studies that a high calcium diet has the potential to reverse fluorosis. This indicator variable is divided into two categories: Healthy and Malnutrition.

- Healthy/balanced diet: 0-2
- Malnutrition/under nutrition: 3-5

Here, there could be a point of discussion as to how to judge whether a person is healthy or undernourished. One is symptoms based approach and other is by height and weight approach. Through symptoms like fatigue, poor concentration, diarrhea etc will help to know whether one is having balanced diet or not and other would be by calculating BMI using height and weight of an individual.

Here one can also be flexible by adding the kind of foods one is having everyday in general. By calculating the amount of calories from the food consumed can also give a rough idea about the diet of a person.

4. Location(Geology)

Geology of location plays a vital role as due to presence of certain rocks and minerals enhances the concentration of fluoride in groundwater as well as soil. The mineral which imparts fluorine into the groundwater has been discussed in the introduction. This indicator variable spatially is divided into two categories:

- Location on fluoride mineral bed: 3-5
- Location on non-fluoride mineral bed: 0-2

5. Education/Awareness/Capacity Development

Education is considered as an indicator variable to assess the fluorosis prevalence as it is observed that having certain level of awareness and education impacts (hinders) the spread of fluorosis. Various studies have been conducted to comprehend the effect of consuming fluoride contaminated food and water on children intelligence and health.

Studies which can be conducted in parallel:

- Consumption of fluoride contaminated water, food and its effect on educational outcomes.

Certain number of schools can be selected in fluoride prevalent zones and non-fluoride prevalent zones. Children's can be divided into three categories. For eg: Standard 3-5, 6-8, and 8-10. A set of questions can be prepared for each category to test the scores. This study would help to know the performance of children, attendance in schools, gender based analysis in terms of score and ability etc.

- Economic studies

The above studies could also help to analyze and estimate the outcome of various programs which are implemented in the grassroots level by the government.

This indicator variable is categorized into two categories:

- ✓ Individual level: 0-5
- ✓ Community level: 0-5

It would be easier to assume weights at community level as judgment can be made by the presence and effective implementation of fluoride preventive programs by Schools, Hospitals, Anganwadi etc. Certain exception cannot be neglected as we have observed in field visits that people are reluctant to consume RO water (provided by Govt.) due to its cost and taste.

6. Interventions

There are several interventions to curb the menace of fluorosis which are been implemented at various areas. The following interventions are most commonly used and are effective in reducing the effect of fluorosis.

- Surface water supply: 1
- Rain water harvesting: 1
- RO plant and usage: 1
- None of the above: 3-5 (any other preventive measure depends of efficacy)

Proxy Study Area: Devanhalli Block (Bengaluru Rural)

As per the availability of coordinate location, Devanhalli Block has been considered as a test study area for the analysis. The study is conducted using assumed Random weights (weights have been given randomly which could contradict with other parameters). *On a scale of 0 to 5, weight has been provided accordingly, where 0 means no impact while 5 shows high impact.*

State Name	District Name	Block Name	Panchayat Name	Village Name	Habitat Name	Latitude	Longitude	Fluoride (ppm)	F weight	Income	Location(Geology)	Nutrition	Interventions	Education
KARNATAKA	BANGALORE RURAL	DEVANHALLI	ANNESWARA	BYCHAPURA	BYCHAPURA	13.2277	77.7166	2.19	3	5	3	3	4	2
KARNATAKA	BANGALORE RURAL	DEVANHALLI	CHANNARAYA PATNA	KONAGINABELE	KONAGINABELE	13.2226	77.8153	2.54	4	4	4	2	3	3
KARNATAKA	BANGALORE RURAL	DEVANHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	13.3150	77.7488	1.50	0	2	2	1	4	4
KARNATAKA	BANGALORE RURAL	DEVANHALLI	JALIGE	ARADESHANA HALLI	ARADESHANA HALLI	13.2218	77.5662	4.72	4	1	1	4	2	1
KARNATAKA	BANGALORE RURAL	DODBALLAPUR	BHAKT HARAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	13.2825	77.6493	5.08	5	3	2	4	3	2

1. Fluoride Concentration in water:

Block Name	Panchayat Name	Village Name	Habitation Name	Fluoride(ppm)	F weight
DEVANHALLI	ANNESWARA	BYCHAPURA	BYCHAPURA	2.19	3.00
DEVANHALLI	CHANNARAYAPATNA	KONAGINABELE	KONAGINABELE	2.54	4.00
DEVANHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	1.50	0.00
DEVANHALLI	JALIGE	ARADESHANAHALLI	ARADESHANAHALLI	4.72	4.00
DODBALLAPUR	BHAKTHARAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	5.08	5.00

Above locations have been selected and random fluoride concentration is provided in the selected locations.

The above figure illustrates fluoride concentration in ground water in all selected villages is above the threshold (>1.5 mg/l). Based on the fluoride concentration, weights have been assigned accordingly and map has been prepared.

2. Income of household:

Block Name	Panchayat Name	Village Name	Habitation Name	Income
DEVANHALLI	ANNESWARA	BYCHAPURA	BYCHAPURA	5
DEVANHALLI	CHANNARAYAPATNA	KONAGINABELE	KONAGINABELE	4
DEVANHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	2
DEVANHALLI	JALIGE	ARADESHANAHALLI	ARADESHANAHALLI	1
DODBALLAPUR	BHAKTHARAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	3

As discussed above in Income section, it can be seen from the figure that highest weight is concentrated around and Byachapura village and it starts decreasing as one touches other villages. So, lower income class people are more in Byachapura village and Konaginabe, middle

class income people are in Harohally and Gundalahalli whereas higher income class people are in Ardeshanahalli.

3. Nutrition

Block Name	Panchayat Name	Village Name	Habitation Name	Nutrition
DEVANHALLI	ANNESWARA	BYCHAPURA	BYCHAPURA	3
DEVANHALLI	CHANNARAYAPATNA	KONAGINABELE	KONAGINABELE	2
DEVANHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	1
DEVANHALLI	JALIGE	ARADESHANAHALLI	ARADESHANAHALLI	4
DODBALLAPUR	BHAKTHARAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	4

The above figure illustrates that people residing in villages Ardeshanahalli and Gundalahalli are deficient of having nutritious food which makes them prone to diseases than other villages.

4. Geology(Location)

Block Name	Panchayat Name	Village Name	Habitation Name	Location(Geology)
DEVANHALLI	ANNESWARA	BYCHAPURA	BYCHAPURA	3
DEVANHALLI	CHANNARAYAPATNA	KONAGINABELE	KONAGINABELE	4
DEVANHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	2
DEVANHALLI	JALIGE	ARADESHANAHALLI	ARADESHANAHALLI	1
DODBALLAPUR	BHAKTHARAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	2

It is assumed that Ardeshanahalli, Gundalahalli and Harohalli are situated in non-fluoride mineral bed while other villages are situated in fluoride mineral bed. So, accordingly, weights have been provided and thematic map is prepared.

5. Awareness/Capacity Development

Block Name	Panchayat Name	Village Name	Habitation Name	Education
DEVANHALLI	ANNESWARA	BYCHAPURA	BYCHAPURA	2
DEVANHALLI	CHANNARAYAPATNA	KONAGINABELE	KONAGINABELE	3
DEVANHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	4
DEVANHALLI	JALIGE	ARADESHANAHALLI	ARADESHANAHALLI	1
DODBALLAPUR	BHAKTHARAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	2

It is observed that Harohalli village residents are least educated and aware about fluorosis and its effects as compared to other villages.

6. Interventions

Block Name	Panchayat Name	Village Name	Habitation Name	Interventions
DEVANHALLI	ANNESWARA	BYCHAPURA	BYCHAPURA	4
DEVANHALLI	CHANNARAYAPATNA	KONAGINABELE	KONAGINABELE	3
DEVANHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	HAROHALLI	4
DEVANHALLI	JALIGE	ARADESHANAHALLI	ARADESHANAHALLI	2
DODBALLAPUR	BHAKTHARAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	GUNDLAHALLY	3

As discussed earlier, here it is assumed that Aradeshanalli village has been provided with certain relief to overcome fluoride prevalence while other villages have not been benefitted.

Methodology

The AHP technique is a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) model which has been adopted here to determine the weights of the thematic maps of the indicator variables discussed and shown above.

An AHP model excel sheet developed by Dr. Klaus D. Goepel and can be found in <http://bpmsg.com> has been used to determine weight in percentage of each indicator variable. Each indicator variable importance is compared with other indicator variable individually and based on one's own experience and judgment corresponding weights are provided. The weights (1-9) of each indicator variable when compared with other variable can be seen below.

		Criteria		more important ?	Scale	
i	j	A	B	A or B	(1-9)	
1	2	Awareness	Geology	B	5	
1	3		income	B	1	
1	4		intervention	B	3	
1	5		nutrition	B	5	
1	6		F weight	B	7	
1	7					
1	8					
2	3	Geology	income	A	7	
2	4		intervention	A	5	
2	5		nutrition	A	1	
2	6		F weight	B	5	
2	7					
2	8					
3	4	income	intervention	B	1	
3	5		nutrition	B	1	
3	6		F weight	B	7	
3	7					
3	8					
4	5	intervention	nutrition	B	1	
4	6		F weight	B	7	
4	7					
4	8					
5	6	nutrition	F weight	B	5	
5	7					
5	8					

Intensity	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two elements contribute equally to the objective
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgment slightly favor one element over another
5	Strong Importance	Experience and judgment strongly favor one element over another
7	Very strong importance	One element is favored very strongly over another, its dominance is demonstrated in practice
9	Extreme importance	The evidence favoring one element over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation
2,4,6,8 can be used to express intermediate values		

The percentage weight of each indicator variable is derived using above scaling method and can be seen below.

Criterion	Comment	Weights	+/-
1 Awareness		3.9%	#####
2 Geology		21.1%	#####
3 income		5.9%	#####
4 intervention		7.2%	#####
5 nutrition		11.4%	#####
6 F weight		50.4%	#####
7		0.0%	0.0%
8		0.0%	0.0%
9	for 9&10 unprotect the input sheets and expand the	0.0%	0.0%
10	question section ("+" in row 66)	0.0%	0.0%

In GIS platform using reclassify and overlay tool above percentage weights are provided to each individual thematic map and risk/vulnerable zone is prepared.

The resultant thematic map shows the areas spread across the Devanhalli block which is categorized into resilient, risk, less vulnerable and high vulnerable zone. As per the indicator variable and assumed weights considered to derive the thematic map, it is seen that Harohalli village comes under resilient zone whereas Ardeshanahalli and Konaginabe comes under highly vulnerable zone.

The policy makers and responsible authorities can use this tool to curb fluorosis in vulnerable zone adopting various possible remedial measures or interventions which suits that region. For eg: a possible intervention at Gundalahalli would be to provide surface water supply and encouraging people to have healthy diet. It is to be noted that all remedial measures should be region specific and it may not be universal in nature. An introduction of certain multivitamins and antioxidants in specific region may reduce risk of fluorosis considering people are exposed to certain amount (<2.5 mg/l) of fluoride.

Framework limitations and other ideas:

- There are might be some variables which could act as a sub variable to the indicator variables taken in the framework.
- We can update this framework by adding other variables like drinking water contamination due to presence of arsenic and nitrate, other prevalent diseases, caste system etc.
- The Devanhalli case study presented above is made based on pure assumption and analysis might be insignificant as five villages were selected, therefore it is required to have more villages to draw a comprehensive picture about vulnerable zone.
- The above framework might work well when it is taken as a district based study while state based study might overlook certain places which might be in risk zone.

Similarly, a framework can be designed where sustainable solutions could be provided based on the problem. It could be named as **Potential Sustainable Remedial Solution Feasibility Assessment framework**. The variable could be:

1. Surface Water Supply
2. Efficient household filtration technique
3. Nutritional intervention
4. Bioremediation
5. Rain water harvesting
6. Other potential techniques
 - Oxidation pond/ditch
 - Wetlands....etc